

HYPERTENSION: MODERN APPROACH TO PATIENT MANAGEMENT ACCORDING TO NEW EUROPEAN GUIDELINES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the innovations of 2024 European Society of Hypertension guidelines, with an emphasis on the paradigm shift in the management of patients with elevated blood pressure (BP). One of the key innovations is the focus on earlier and more aggressive intervention for patients with "elevated BP," which is reflected in lower target BP values and stricter control. The article provides a detailed examination of changes in the stratification of patients with elevated BP, the use of models for assessing cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk, and treatment approaches based on individual risk rather than solely on BP thresholds. The necessity for revising clinical approaches in light of these new recommendations is emphasized, which is of significant importance for primary healthcare in the prevention and reduction of cardiovascular complications (CVD).

Keywords: hypertension; Elevated blood pressure; Risk factors; Personalized approach; Risk stratification; Threshold values; Blood pressure target levels.

Justification

The relevance of the topic of arterial hypertension (AH) remains high, considering its role as a leading risk factor for cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), which are responsible for a significant burden of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Over the past few decades, a large amount of data has been accumulated confirming the connection between blood pressure (BP) levels and the development of complications such as stroke, myocardial infarction, heart failure, and other vascular disorders. In the context of global changes in approaches to AH treatment, especially in light of the new clinical recommendations from the European Society of Hypertension for 2024, it becomes crucial to reconsider models of patient management.

Special attention in the modern recommendations is given to changing the treatment paradigm, particularly the transition from the traditional approach based on fixed BP thresholds to a more flexible risk stratification approach, tailored to the individual characteristics of the patient. According to the new recommendations, aggressive treatment of arterial hypertension should begin even at lower BP levels (120-139/70-89 mm Hg) if the patient is at high risk of cardiovascular events. This approach reflects a broader shift in clinical practice, aimed not only at achieving target BP levels but also at reducing overall morbidity and mortality from CVDs in the population.

The recommendations presented in 2024 also emphasize the need to use risk prediction models (such as SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP), which allow for a more accurate assessment of the likelihood of adverse outcomes based on various risk factors, including age, gender, smoking, cholesterol levels, and the presence of comorbidities such as diabetes and chronic kidney disease.

This allows for not only more accurate identification of indications for initiating antihypertensive therapy but also for individualizing treatment approaches, improving therapeutic outcomes.

In light of these changes, this article aims to analyze the innovations in the 2024 recommendations for the treatment of patients with elevated blood pressure. It provides a critical review of approaches to risk stratification, the implementation of new methods for predicting cardiovascular events, and the assessment of the benefits of early and aggressive intervention. The findings of this study may be useful for clinicians in making more informed decisions when treating patients with elevated BP and for further improving medical care practices for arterial hypertension.

Objective

The objective of this analytical review is to examine the new 2024 recommendations from the European Society of Hypertension, highlighting innovations, particularly in risk stratification, BP thresholds and targets necessary for optimal antihypertensive therapy, and to assist primary care physicians in becoming familiar with the changes in the new clinical guidelines.

Methods

The analysis includes publications from the PubMed (MEDLINE) database using keywords such as "arterial hypertension," "risk factors," "target organ damage," and "risk stratification," covering a search depth of 10 years (2014-2024). A total of 149 publications were reviewed, and 25 sources most relevant to the topic of this article were selected.

In May 2024, the European Society of Hypertension (ESH) Congress presented new guidelines on "Managing patients with elevated blood pressure and hypertension." Notably, the term "arterial" was excluded from the title of the document, marking a step towards simplifying and unifying the guidelines. The term "hypertension" already implies elevated blood pressure (BP). The new title better reflects the clinical essence of these recommendations, emphasizing the general rise in pressure, including not only arterial hypertension but also other types, such as pulmonary hypertension. The latter is not addressed by these recommendations.

A global study on the burden of diseases (Global Burden of Disease, GBD) showed that over a 29-year period (1990-2019), high systolic blood pressure (SBP) became the leading risk factor for mortality worldwide, accounting for 10.8 million deaths (19.2% of all deaths). This is primarily due to target organ damage caused by arterial hypertension (TOD), which results from prolonged high BP and/or hypertension.

In view of these findings, it is necessary to focus on patients at the "elevated BP" stage (120-139/70-89 mm Hg) to prevent the development and progression of TOD. The introduction of this term in the new guidelines underscores the importance of early diagnosis and prevention when BP is at the borderline level but has not yet reached hypertension thresholds. Even asymptomatic patients with "elevated BP" may have an increased risk of cardiovascular complications (CVD). Identifying and controlling AH at this stage can prevent progression to persistent hypertension and the associated target organ damage, such as to the heart, kidneys, and brain. Early intervention, including lifestyle modification and, if necessary, medication helps slow the disease's progression and improves long-term outcomes.

Conversely, the "non-elevated BP" category (<120/<70 mm Hg) includes fewer individuals at risk for CVD. Furthermore, there are no clinical studies proving the benefits of antihypertensive treatment for this category of patients. It is essential to remember that hypertension categories reflect treatment approaches rather than prognosis, which is why the new guidelines avoid using

terms like "normal BP," "optimal BP," or "normotension," which could be misleading regarding prognostic significance.

Non-Elevated BP	Elevated BP	Hypertension
Office BP		
SBP <120 mm Hg and DBP <70 mm Hg	SBP 120-139 mm Hg or DBP 70-89 mm Hg	SBP ≥140 mm Hg or DBP ≥90 mm Hg
DHP BP		
SBP <120 mm Hg and DBP <70 mm Hg	SBP 120-134 mm Hg or DBP 70-84 mm Hg	SBP ≥135 mm Hg or DBP ≥85 mm Hg
ABPM		
Daytime SBP <120 mm Hg and Daytime DBP <70 mm Hg	Daytime SBP 120-134 mm Hg or Daytime DBP 70-84 mm Hg	Daytime SBP ≥135 mm Hg or Daytime DBP ≥85 mm Hg

The ESH 2024 guidelines reflect a transition from the traditional approach, where patient stratification was based on blood pressure (BP) thresholds, to a model of patient stratification based on individual risk. This approach is particularly relevant for patients with "elevated BP" (120-139/70-89 mm Hg), which did not meet the criteria for hypertension in previous guidelines, leading to the underestimation of this group. It has been shown that even in patients with BP below 140/90 mm Hg, there is a significant occurrence of cardiovascular events, which aligns with data on the substantial increase in the risk of adverse outcomes as BP rises. The logarithmic relationship between BP and the risk of adverse outcomes supports the rationale for therapy in patients with BP above 120/70 mm Hg, if their 10-year cardiovascular risk is ≥10%. It is important to pay attention to patients with elevated BP, who are typically younger, as their absolute cardiovascular risk depends on additional risk factors (such as diabetes, chronic kidney disease (CKD), hypercholesterolemia, etc.). In these cases, the use of formalized risk models becomes key for clarifying indications for therapy initiation. Risk assessment models such as SCORE2 allow for the consideration of demographic and clinical factors, simplifying the decision-making process regarding therapy.

Managing patients with "elevated BP" in line with modern approaches requires integrating individual cardiovascular risk assessment to make decisions about therapy initiation. The ESH 2024 guidelines highlight groups of patients for whom the initiation of antihypertensive therapy (AHT) is appropriate, even without diagnosed hypertension. These groups include patients with:

Moderate or severe chronic kidney disease (CKD): eGFR <60 mL/min/1.73 m² or albuminuria ≥30 mg/g (≥3 mg/mmol);

Established cardiovascular diseases (CVD) (ischemic heart disease, cerebrovascular diseases, peripheral artery disease, heart failure);

Target organ damage (TOD);

Type 1 and type 2 diabetes. In this case, to identify individuals with a lower cardiovascular risk (<10% CVD risk over 10 years), who may not require AHT (especially those under 60), the SCORE2-Diabetes model should be used;

Familial hypercholesterolemia – probable or diagnosed.

For patients without these conditions, assessing 10-year CVD risk using validated models like SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP is a key step. The accuracy of these models is higher compared to

conventional clinical assessment or counting individual risk factors. SCORE2 is used for patients aged 40-69, and SCORE2-OP is used for those over 70. Both tools consider both fatal and non-fatal CVD events. A CVD risk $\geq 10\%$ using SCORE2/SCORE2-OP is the threshold for decisions about starting AHT in patients with elevated BP. Studies show the effectiveness of BP reduction in this risk group.

Strengthening the use of risk stratification tools in the new guidelines also supports a personalized approach to treating patients with elevated BP, thereby improving the effectiveness of CVD prevention and long-term outcomes.

More Intensive BP Control. For most patients, a target BP level of $<130/80$ mm Hg is strongly recommended. For those at high cardiovascular risk (CVR), a target systolic BP of 120-129 mm Hg (if well tolerated) is suggested, reflecting data from recent studies (SPRINT, HOPE-3). This approach significantly reduces the risk of cardiovascular complications (CVD). However, therapy should be adapted to the individual characteristics of the patient, including treatment tolerance and the risk of side effects.

Studies such as SPRINT have shown significant reductions in CVR when more stringent BP targets are achieved, especially systolic BP in the 120-129 mm Hg range, compared to traditional targets (<140 mm Hg). Systolic BP in the range of 120-129 mm Hg, according to meta-analyses, is associated with a reduced risk of strokes, myocardial infarctions, and heart failure. This target BP range (120-129/70-79 mm Hg) is more flexible and accounts for individual differences in therapy tolerance and the possibility of minimizing side effects, such as orthostatic hypotension or kidney damage.

In contrast, for patients with a high risk of side effects, such as those with severe chronic kidney failure (eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73 m²), symptomatic orthostatic hypotension, or frailty, as well as those over 85 years old, strict BP control may be inappropriate due to reduced tolerance for intensive therapy and a high risk of non-cardiovascular mortality. If life expectancy is less than 3 years, the focus shifts to quality of life rather than long-term BP goals.

Thus, the main changes in BP target levels in the 2024 guidelines involve revising the threshold for starting and target levels for antihypertensive therapy. Recent research highlights the benefits of more intensive BP reduction to the range of 120-129/70-79 mm Hg, which is associated with a reduced risk of cardiovascular diseases. However, target levels should consider age, frailty, comorbidities, and the patient's individual circumstances. Consequently, therapy individualization and regular assessment of therapy tolerance remain key principles in the new guidelines.

Conclusion. The ESH 2024 guidelines for managing patients with elevated blood pressure represent a significant advancement in the approaches to diagnosing, preventing, and treating hypertension. The innovations emphasize the importance of early diagnosis, individual cardiovascular risk assessment, and personalized therapy. The introduction of the concept of "elevated BP" draws attention to patient categories that were previously underestimated in terms of cardiovascular risk. This enables early intervention and the prevention of complications, such as target organ damage. The use of formalized risk models (e.g., SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP) facilitates decisions about starting antihypertensive therapy based on the integration of demographic, clinical, and behavioral factors.

Special emphasis is placed on adapting treatment goals based on the patient's individual characteristics, including treatment tolerance and the risk of side effects. For most patients, a target BP of $<130/80$ mm Hg is optimal, while for those at high risk of cardiovascular complications,

stricter target levels (120-129 mm Hg) are recommended, provided therapy is well tolerated. However, the guidelines stress the need for flexibility in prescribing therapy, especially for patients with special clinical conditions (e.g., severe chronic kidney failure, symptomatic orthostatic hypotension, frailty) or elderly individuals. For such patients, the focus is on maintaining quality of life rather than strict BP control.

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